

Figure S1. Genetic linkage map developed in the recombinant inbred TUM population from 842 SNPs obtained from genotyping-by-sequencing.

Figure S2. F2 progenies obtained from the complementary crosses between selected TUMRILs: TUM051xTUM101 and TU051xTUM170. Labels in seed progenies (F2 seeds) images indicate the ID of the F1 plant by which they were produced.

Figure S3. A simple schematic diagram of flavonoid biosynthesis pathway [adapted from Petroni and Tornelli (2011) and Reinprecht et al. (2013)].

ANS: anthocyanidin synthase; ANR: anthocyanidin reductase; AOMT: anthocyanin O-methyltransferase; DRF: dihydroflavonol 4-reductase; F3H: flavanone 3-hydroxylase; F3'H: flavonoid 3'-hydroxylase; F3'5'H: flavonoid 3'5'-hydroxylase; FLS: flavonol synthase; FS: flavone synthase; LAR: anthocyanidin reductase; LDOX: leucocyanidin dioxygenase; UFGT: UDP-glucose:flavonoid 3-O-glucosyltransferase. Color or color range in the different compounds represents its visible color. Yellow shading highlights the branch of the anthocyanin biosynthesis pathway affected by the loss of function of the F3'5'H enzyme.

Figure S4. Multiple sequence alignment of *PhvuI.006G018800* gene for the genotypes TU and Musica using G19833 as reference sequence. Points indicate identical residues. ‘N’ represents nucleotide positions not determined in this study. Coding regions are highlight in yellow boxes.


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      1050      1060      1070      1080      1090      1100      1110      1120
Phvul.006G018800 AAGTTATTTAAGAGTAAACTATAATGATAATTTATAAGATTTCTTTTAAATCATATTTATATCTCTGCTTTTTTTTA
TU
Musica
      1130      1140      1150      1160      1170      1180      1190      1200
Phvul.006G018800 CTATTATAGTAATCTCTCACTACCAAGGTGTGCAAGTATAATGTTTTTAAACTTAGAAAAAAAAAACGTGCAATGTA
TU
Musica
      1210      1220      1230      1240      1250      1260      1270      1280
Phvul.006G018800 AAAATCGGTGACGATGTAATAGTTTAAAAAACGAATGTTTGTTTAAAGTTTAAAGAAGTTGGGATTTGGACGTAATTTGA
TU
Musica
      1290      1300      1310      1320      1330      1340      1350      1360
Phvul.006G018800 GAAAAGGTGAAGAGATGTAATGGAAGTTACTCTTGTAGTAGATAAGTTAAATTGTTTTAAATATAAGGTTATGAGTTC
TU
Musica
      1370      1380      1390      1400      1410      1420      1430      1440
Phvul.006G018800 CCTATTTTTATTTTACAAAGTACATTTTTAAACCATGATTCATTCAAAAAATCAGTTAATTTTCAAATAATTACAAAT
TU
Musica
      1450      1460      1470      1480      1490      1500      1510      1520
Phvul.006G018800 TGTTTGATAACTTTGATACACTTAAATATGTATGAACAAACCTTTCTCTAAAAAATTTTAAATGAATTTTTTAAAAAGTT
TU
Musica
      1530      1540      1550      1560      1570      1580      1590      1600
Phvul.006G018800 AAAATTTATATAATAAGTTATTTTAAATATTTACATTTATTATATATATATATATAATAAATTAATTAATTTTA
TU
Musica
      1610      1620      1630      1640      1650      1660      1670      1680
Phvul.006G018800 ACTTAAAAAATATTTTACTTTTCATCTTTATATTTTAAAAAATCATAAAGAATTACCCAAACATCCTTTTTAAATA
TU
Musica
      1690      1700      1710      1720      1730      1740      1750      1760
Phvul.006G018800 GTTTAAGAAATGAATTTCAATGATACACAAGTTTTTTCTCCTTGCAATTAGTTTTTTATTAGGATGAATTTGTTACGTC
TU
Musica
      1770      1780      1790      1800      1810      1820      1830      1840
Phvul.006G018800 TTATATATTAATTAAGTTAAATATTATTTTATAAAAAAATACTAATATCTAAAAAGTTTATATCTTAACATAAATTT
TU
Musica
      1850      1860      1870      1880      1890      1900      1910      1920
Phvul.006G018800 ATAAAAATATTTCTAAATTTATATCCAACATTAACAATCATTTAAATTATTATAATTATCTTAAATTCAAATTAAGTCT
TU
Musica
      1930      1940      1950      1960      1970      1980      1990      2000
Phvul.006G018800 TTCATTATAAATTAATGATTAATTTAAAAATTAATAAGTTAATTAATATCAATTTAAAAATTTATTTATAA
TU
Musica
      2010      2020      2030      2040      2050      2060      2070      2080
Phvul.006G018800 ATTTTATTAATAA AAAAAATATTTTAAATGTCAATAATTTTTTAACTATAAAATAGTATGTAAATTAATTTTAA
TU
Musica

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                2090      2100      2110      2120      2130      2140      2150      2160
Phvul.006G018800  TCTTTAAATTAATTTAATAACTTTCCGAAAATGATGTGTTTTGGGGTTAAAAATAAAGAAGAATGGAAAAATGAGAAGTAGA
TU
Musica            .....TC..G.T.....
                2170      2180      2190      2200      2210      2220      2230      2240
Phvul.006G018800  AAAAGTTAGAATTTGAATAAGAGAGTTGTAAGTAAAAGTTGGTAGTTTGGATTGATGGTTGTTGACAGGATATGGTGT
TU
Musica            .....T.....A.....G.....
                2250      2260      2270      2280      2290      2300      2310      2320
Phvul.006G018800  TGCTGATTACGGATCAAGGTGGAAGCTGCTGAGGAAACTGAGCAACCTGCACATGCTGGGAGGAAAGGCTGTGGAAGAGT
TU
Musica            .....
                2330      2340      2350      2360      2370      2380      2390      2400
Phvul.006G018800  GGAGCAAGGTTGAGATGAAGAGATGGTTCAGATGATTGGTACGCTGTACGAATGCAGCAAGAAGGGTGAAGCTGTGGTG
TU
Musica            .....A.....
                2410      2420      2430      2440      2450      2460      2470      2480
Phvul.006G018800  GTGCCTGAAATCTTGACCTACTCCATGGCCAAACATGATAGGGAAAGGTTATACTGAGTCGTCGAGTGTGTTGAGACGAAGGG
TU
Musica            .....
                2490      2500      2510      2520      2530      2540      2550      2560
Phvul.006G018800  TTCGGAGTCAAACGAGTTC AAGGACATGGTGGTGGAGCTCATGACTGTTGCAGGCTACTTCAACATCGGCGATTTCATAC
TU
Musica            .....T.....
                2570      2580      2590      2600      2610      2620      2630      2640
Phvul.006G018800  CCTTCTTGGCCAAATTTGACTTGAAGGGATTGAGCGTGGGATGAAGCAGTTGCACAAGAAGTTTGATAGGTTGTTGACG
TU
Musica            .....
                2650      2660      2670      2680      2690      2700      2710      2720
Phvul.006G018800  AAGATGATTCAAGAGCATGTTGCTTCCAAGCACAAGAGAAACGATAAACCTGATTTCTTGGACATGGTCATGGCTCATT
TU
Musica            .....G.....
                2730      2740      2750      2760      2770      2780      2790      2800
Phvul.006G018800  TGGCGAACAAACAGACGCTCATCACGACAACATCACTTATCAACATCAAAGCTCTGCTTTTGGTACGCATCACTCTAA
TU
Musica            .....A.....
                2810      2820      2830      2840      2850      2860      2870      2880
Phvul.006G018800  CATCTCTCTCTTATCACCTTCCACCCTTGTGTA AACACA AACTACTGTGTGGGATATAGGTTACATAAATGTCCC
TU
Musica            .....
                2890      2900      2910      2920      2930      2940      2950      2960
Phvul.006G018800  AGTTTATTAATTTTATTCTTTATTAATTA AAAAAAAAAA AACTATACACTATGATGGCCACAAGTTATTAGTGAGTAAGAATA
TU
Musica            .....G.....T.....A.....
                2970      2980      2990      3000      3010      3020      3030      3040
Phvul.006G018800  CTAAAAAAGTGTGCTAGGGACATGCTTTTAAACATCTTAGTTATATATGCCTACATCTTAGTTTTAAATATATTATTATT
TU
Musica            .....T.....
                3050      3060      3070      3080      3090      3100      3110      3120
Phvul.006G018800  TAAATATTATTTTATATTATTTAATTATAAATTTACTTTTTATTATATATATATATATATATATATTTACTTTTAAAT
TU
Musica            .....

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      3130      3140      3150      3160      3170      3180      3190      3200
Phvul.006G018800 TTTTACATAAAAAATTGTGTGCAATTATGAGAGTTCTCGAACTATTTCTTTATGAGTAATTAATGCATCAGAAATTTTGT
TU                A.....NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            A.....NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      3210      3220      3230      3240      3250      3260      3270      3280
Phvul.006G018800 TCTCTGTGACGTATAATTTGTAGGTGAAAGAACTGATTGCAACGTCACCTTTTAAAGAGAGATATACGTACACTTTGCAT
TU                NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      3290      3300      3310      3320      3330      3340      3350      3360
Phvul.006G018800 TTTGAATGAAAAGTAACAGATACAAAATTAGAAATTTCTTCAATTAGAATACATAAAAAGTATAGTCTTATTATTATTATT
TU                NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      3370      3380      3390      3400      3410      3420      3430      3440
Phvul.006G018800 ATTTCTTTTCTATGAAAAATTCAAATCATGTCAATGTAATTTATACCAACTCTCCCTCATCATCGAAGTGTCTTG
TU                NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      3450      3460      3470      3480      3490      3500      3510      3520
Phvul.006G018800 GAAAGAAAAA TCATTTACAAAAGTTGAGTCTAAATTTAAGTGAACAAAATTTTCAGTATTCCTTAAATATAATAAACAT
TU                A.....A.....
Musica            A.....A.....

      3530      3540      3550      3560      3570      3580      3590      3600
Phvul.006G018800 ATGATATCAACAAACTTTCAGTGGTCGAAACAATTAATGTTAATATGTTTTATATAATTTACCTAATTCCTTGTACTAGCG
TU                G.....
Musica            G.....

      3610      3620      3630      3640      3650      3660      3670      3680
Phvul.006G018800 TAGGAAGAAAAGTTGATAACCAACATAGTTAAGTATTAAAGGACAAAGTAAGGGTTGTACATGTCGTACGTGAATTAATAAAT
TU                A.....A.....
Musica            A.....A.....

      3690      3700      3710      3720      3730      3740      3750      3760
Phvul.006G018800 TACCCACGTCGAGTGTTTTCTGTGTAATAATTCACATGATAGCCTTTAAATGCTCACTGTACGTTAAATGCTCACTATA
TU                A.....A.....
Musica            A.....A.....

      3770      3780      3790      3800      3810      3820      3830      3840
Phvul.006G018800 CAATAAATATGTTTAAAAAATATAGATTATTAATTCAAATTTATAAATATCTAAATTTATATTAATTTAAGTTTATTTA
TU                C.....A.....G.....
Musica            C.....A.....G.....

      3850      3860      3870      3880      3890      3900      3910      3920
Phvul.006G018800 AATAAATTTATCTCAAATCCAAATTCATATCCAATCTATATAAATTAGATTTAGATTAGATATTAGATCGGATATATTTTA
TU                T.....C.....T.....
Musica            T.....T.....C.....T.....

      3930      3940      3950      3960      3970      3980      3990      4000
Phvul.006G018800 AAATTATTTAAAATAGATTTTGTGAGCTGAGTTAAATCAGACTCAGGTCGAACTAAGTTAGTCCAAACTTAGGCTAGTTCGA
TU                NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            A.....T.....C.....A.....N.....

      4010      4020      4030      4040      4050      4060      4070      4080
Phvul.006G018800 GTCGATCTGAACTATGTGCGAGTTAAATCGATTCAATCCAAGTCGAATCAATAAGCACGGGAACAGGTCACCAAAATC
TU                NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4090      4100      4110      4120      4130      4140      4150      4160
Phvul.006G018800 GATCAAGATCCATATCGAATCGAATTTGGTCCGACTGAGATCGAACTGATTCGACCCATGCATAGGTCAGGCCAATCAGC
TU                NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica            NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

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      4170      4180      4190      4200      4210      4220      4230      4240
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 CTTAACTCCTATCGAGCAAATCGATCTAAACTTAACTGATTCAACTCAGATCCAATATGAGCGGATTCTAGATACCATAT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4250      4260      4270      4280      4290      4300      4310      4320
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 GCTTACTATACATATGGTCTTACCTTCAATTTTGTTATTTTATTAATTTTCTCACCTTCCACTTAAGAAAAGAAT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4330      4340      4350      4360      4370      4380      4390      4400
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 TAAAAATGAAAACCTTTATCTCTTCCAAAATTCGCCCCGCTACCAAAACAGAGTGGAACCTCTTCTTAAAAGAAGAA
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4410      4420      4430      4440      4450      4460      4470      4480
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 ATTGGACTCTCGGCAAATTAATTAAGAATTCCTCATACCTCTATGTGCATTTTCATATATATTTTTTAAATTCAAT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4490      4500      4510      4520      4530      4540      4550      4560
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 CCTATTACTATTCATTACAGAAAATCATAAAATAAAACTAAATTTATAAACAAAAATAATTAAGTTGGCTATAGTGACT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4570      4580      4590      4600      4610      4620      4630      4640
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 AAATTAGAGACCATTTTAGGAACAAATAATTTTTGTTTCTAAATTAGTTTCTATTATTGTTAGATGATTTCTAAATT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4650      4660      4670      4680      4690      4700      4710      4720
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 AGCAACCAAGGTTTTTGCTACCAAATTTAGAACTAAATAATTGGTAATTAAAACCTTGGTAGCTAATTAGATATCAATT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4730      4740      4750      4760      4770      4780      4790      4800
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 TAGAAACCATTTAACAATAATAAAACTAATTTAGAAACCAAAAATTTATTTAGTCCCTAAAATGGTCTCTAATTTAGTC
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      4810      4820      4830      4840      4850      4860      4870      4880
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 ACTATAGCAACTAATTTATTTATGTTTCTAAAATAGTTTTTATTTTCATGATTTCCCTGTAGTAATTATTATATTATAAG
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
      TGA.A...A.GA...C...A...T...G...

      4890      4900      4910      4920      4930      4940      4950      4960
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 TATATATTAGTGTTTTGTGTTTGGTTGAAAGTAATAATGGTTTGTTCCTCATTTTTAAGTAGTCTTGGTTGTTTATGATG
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
      TT...G...G...

      4970      4980      4990      5000      5010      5020      5030      5040
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 GTAGTAGATAATTGATGGTTGTTGATGATAAATATTGATGGTTGAGATAAGTTTATGGTGTGTTTACTGTTTGTGTTT
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      5050      5060      5070      5080      5090      5100      5110      5120
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 TGTTCCTTATTTTTCTCATTTATTTTATATATCAAAATGTAATCAATCAATCAATCTCTTATATAATATAATTC
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

      5130      5140      5150      5160      5170      5180      5190      5200
    .....|
Phvul.006G018800 ATATTGTATAATTCAAAATATATTTAAAATTACATCTGGATTGTATAAATAAGAAGTTATTACTTCATTCAAAAATACC
TU NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN
Musica NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

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	5210	5220	5230	5240	5250	5260	5270	5280
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	TTCTAAATTATACGTACAAAAGAATTACAAAACATAAAAAAAAAAAAAATCAAATACCTCACTCAAAAAGAATGTGGTTGTAT							
Musica	NN							
Musica	NN							
	5370	5380	5390	5400	5410	5420	5430	5440
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	AAGGATAAAAATGAGTATTCACGTTTAATGTGAAAGTGTAGGAGGAAGCTTGAGAATTGAAGACAAAAACCTTTTAAGGT							
Musica	NNNNNNNNNNN.....							
	5450	5460	5470	5480	5490	5500	5510	5520
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	ACGGAGGTGGGTGAGGAATTTGCCAACATAAATTTTAGTGACAGTCGTCCTGAAGACCAAAAAGCATACCACAAACTTGT							
Musica							
	5530	5540	5550	5560	5570	5580	5590	5600
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	CCTTCAAAAAGATTGAAAACAAATCCAGAATTAGACTTCCAAATTTGGCTTTCTAAGAGCCAAATTTTGATTGGGATAT							
Musica							
	5610	5620	5630	5640	5650	5660	5670	5680
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	GCAATAAAGGAACATGAAAATGCAGGTGGAATTTCACTTCCCACAACATAAATCTCACTGTAAACATTAAAAAGTGCA							
Musica							
	5690	5700	5710	5720	5730	5740	5750	5760
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	GTCTGAAAAATAAATCAGTGGAACAATTTCCAAAAGATGTTACTGCGGGTAAAGTTTCACCTGGTGCAATTTGGTAAA							
Musica							
	5770	5780	5790	5800	5810	5820	5830	5840
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	ATGGTGTTCGAAGATTCAGGAAAAATCTCTGTTTATAATAAATAAGTGGGATCATATTTTTTTTATTAGATTTTACAAG							
Musica							
	5850	5860	5870	5880	5890	5900	5910	5920
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	CCTAATTTATTTTCGATTAATTTGAGTGGATTGAGTAATATTATCTAAAAATTTAGTATTTAAAAGAGAGATTTATGGAATA							
Musica							
	5930	5940	5950	5960	5970	5980	5990	6000
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	ATAAAGTAAAGAAATGGATGTTTGTGTGGAACAGAACCATTTCACAGCAGGAAGTACACATCTTCAAGCATCATAGAG							
Musica							
	6010	6020	6030	6040	6050	6060	6070	6080
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	TGGTCCTTGGCAGAGATGCTGAAGAATCCAAGCATCATGAAGAAGGCTCAGGAGGAAATGGACCAAGTGATAGGAAGGGA							
Musica							
	6090	6100	6110	6120	6130	6140	6150	6160
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	GCGTCGCCTTAAAGAATCCGACATTCCAACCTTCCCTACTTCCCAAGCCATATGCAAAGAGACCTACAGAAAGCACCTT							
Musica							
	6170	6180	6190	6200	6210	6220	6230	6240
Phvul.006G018800							
TU	TCAACCCCTCTCAACCTCCCTCGAATCTCCAACCAACCATGCCAAGTTAACGGCTTTTACATCCCCAAGAACACTCGTTT							
Musica							

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        6250      6260      6270      6280      6290      6300      6310      6320
Phvul.006G018800  GAGCGTCAACATCTGGGCCATAGGAAGAGACCCCAAGTGTGGGAGAGGCCCTTGGAGTTTAAGCCAGAGAGGTTCTTGA
TU
Musica
        6330      6340      6350      6360      6370      6380      6390      6400
Phvul.006G018800  GTGGGAAGAACAAAATGATCGAACACGTTGGGAATGACTTCGAGCTCATACCCTTTGGTGTGGCCGAAGGATCTGCGCA
TU
Musica
        6410      6420      6430      6440      6450      6460      6470      6480
Phvul.006G018800  GGGACCAGAAATGGGGATTGTGTTAGTGCACCTACATTTTGGGCACTTTGTGCATTCCTTTGATTGAAACTGCCACATGA
TU
Musica
        6490      6500      6510      6520      6530      6540      6550      6560
Phvul.006G018800  AGTGGGGGACTTGAACATGGAAGAGACCTTTGGCCTTGCCTTGCAGAAAAGGTTCCCTTGTGCTTTTCGTTACTCCTA
TU
Musica
        6570      6580      6590      6600      6610      6620      6630      6640
Phvul.006G018800  GGTTGAACCCATTGCTTACATTCCCTTAGATTATAGATATATAACATATATA TAGCTACTCAATAAGTTTTGTGTTG
TU
Musica
        6650      6660      6670      6680      6690      6700      6710      6720
Phvul.006G018800  TTGCACAATCGTTGTTGCTTCTCATGTTGTGTGTTTTTAATCTTTTGTGGTTTCTGATTTTTATTCCATGTATAAAT
TU
Musica
        6730      6740      6750      6760      6770      6780      6790
Phvul.006G018800  GTGTAATTCAGTATATCTTGTGTTTGGGTTAATTATGATTTATGTAATTCATGGTGGACTTAGTCTTTTTAA
TU
Musica

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Figure S5. Multiple sequence alignment of *Phvu1.008G038400* gene for the genotypes TU and Musica using G19833 as reference sequence. Points indicate identical residues. ‘N’ represents nucleotide positions not determined in this study. Coding regions are highlight in yellow boxes.


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      2010      2020      2030      2040      2050      2060      2070      2080
Phvul.008G038400  GCTTTTGCCACGTATTTATTATTTTCATATTATTTATTATTTATTAAAACCTTCGGGATAAAAATATCAAAATAACAACAC
TU  .....G...

      2090      2100      2110      2120      2130      2140      2150      2160
Phvul.008G038400  CTTTACATAATTGTGAACGCAGGTGGTCCCTGATTGCAGGAAGACTTCGGGAAGAACTTCAAATGATGTGAAAAATTAC
TU  .C.....T.....A.....G.....

      2170      2180      2190      2200      2210      2220      2230      2240
Phvul.008G038400  TGGAACACCTACACACGACGTAAATTACACTCTCAGAACAGAGTAAAGCAATCAACATCAAAAA-CTTGTCCCAACTTAC
TU  .....C...A.....A.....A.....

      2250      2260      2270      2280      2290      2300      2310      2320
Phvul.008G038400  TGCAAGGCGAATTTATAAACACTTCCAAAGTTGGTGTAGTAAAGAAGGTGCAGCTGCTTCGTCAAATTGGTGGGAAACT
TU  .A.....A.G.....

      2330      2340      2350      2360      2370      2380      2390      2400
Phvul.008G038400  CTGTGTGATGAGAAATTACAGTGAACAATACATGCTTCTTTGGAGAGGAAGATGCGGTGTTTGATGAACATATGGAATCA
TU  .....T.....A.....GA.....

      2410      2420      2430      2440      2450      2460      2470      2480
Phvul.008G038400  ACAACTTACTTCAATTGATTCTCACTTCTTACAGAAGCTGAAACTTGGAGCCAATCTTCTTGACCTAGAAATTAATT
TU  .....T.....A.

      2490      2500      2510
Phvul.008G038400  AGTATATATATTGTATATTTATGTATGTGTGGTG
TU  .....

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